

ERICXPLORE PUBLISHERS INTERNATIONAL AND TECHNOLOGY

ERICXPLORE JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Vol 1, Issue 1 (2) Dec 2024

Available online at: www.ericolutions.com

The Primitive and Brutal Nature of Humanity in the Age of Technology

Dr Eric Kwasi Elliason, Post PhD Research Scholar, Kennedy University, St Lucia.

Email: manericus2017@gmail.com

Introduction

In a time when technology has increased, it would be expected that people have moved away from being primitive and brutal. However, despite all the progress in science, communication, and social development, dark undercurrents of human behaviour still lurk. This article will look at some of the primitive and brutal sides of humanity that persist despite living in an age full of technology, such as wars, racial discrimination, aggression against others, killings, hatred, and resentment. The intention is to identify these elements and determine why they continue thriving and what that implies for our global society.

Wars and Conflicts: A Legacy of Violence

Throughout history, there have been many wars and conflicts among humans that reflect our violent and brutal nature. This is still evident despite all the technological and global communication advancements made by man, as he has not shown any signs of reducing his warlike behaviour but instead found ways to make it more destructive through technology. The United Nations was created as a worldwide body dedicated to peacekeeping and conflict resolution through diplomacy, yet this has not eliminated warfare as an option. Presently, in the Middle East, Africa, and Eastern Europe, violent confrontations are taking place, thereby proving that violence is still used to settle disputes (Galtung,

1996). Technology could not prevent people from fighting in Iraq and Afghanistan; these two battles only showed how limited modern gadgets can be when it comes to controlling human aggression, which arises out of multifaceted political, religious, or economic interests coupled with intricate interrelationships between them, all resulting into massive deaths tolls alongside widespread physical damages too. The truth is that drones, together with other precision-guided missiles, do indeed enhance efficiency during wars but without reducing their savagery since many innocent lives get lost during such operations, thus leading to humanitarian crises (Singer, 2009). This part will explore what causes wars and conflicts among individuals or nations, the effects of scientific discoveries, and the continuous tradition of using force to settle international disputes.

For thousands of years, it has been said that war never changes. This is true when looking at ancient texts and archaeological evidence that depict battles and conquests from the most remote periods (Keeley, 1996). Primitive societies often engaged in warfare over resources, territory, or power – a pattern that continues today. Therefore, violence is not just something happening today but rather constitutes an integral part

of human civilization; it affects international relations between countries and forces them to settle their disagreements through armaments. As time passed, so did wars change due to societal development and technological advancements, which always proved significant in altering how the war was conducted, increasing its destructiveness and scale in many cases. For example, gunpowder, artillery, firearms, etc, were some inventions that transformed medieval warfare, making it more intense (McNeill, 1982). During the Industrial Revolution, there came mechanized warfare and advanced weapons caused terrible wars like WWI or WWII.

In the previous century, we witnessed unprecedented levels of violence in global conflicts such as World War I, World War II, and the Cold War, displaying modern societies' ability to deal with large-scale wars (Hogan,1996). The use of atomic bombs against Japan represented a turning point because they showed us how much damage can be done by one weapon alone, thus forever changing our idea about what is possible during armed engagements (Schlosser, 2013). Throughout the 20th century, various nations raced each other to amass nuclear arsenals leading up until the collapse of the USSR, therefore indicating

danger associated with any new technology if not appropriately handled (Clapper, 2018).

Things have continued there; however, contemporary times continue to be characterized by increased reliance upon technological innovations during engagements among different adversaries around the globe. Precision-guided missiles and drone cyberwarfare are but a few examples of era game-changers as far as battlefield supremacy is concerned. While these might bring about better accuracy rates, they also create fresh ethical dilemmas besides legal issues surrounding their utilization (Singer, 2009).

One frequently used technological advancement in military operations is drones, which enable countries to carry out more targeted airstrikes. Nonetheless, many times, civilians get killed when such strikes are conducted, leading to questions regarding the morality behind remote-controlled battles and the likelihood of raising anti-western sentiments among affected areas (Shaw, 2016). Also, cyber warfare is another dimension through which conflicts have been fought, with states employing these means to disrupt essential services, steal classified data, or even propagate fake news stories (Clapper, 2018).

Nevertheless, beyond technology, wars remain very costly in terms of lives lost, people displaced from their homes, and infrastructure destroyed during the fighting. Ultimately, it is always innocent civilians who pay the highest price for such events, becoming refugees or internally displaced persons due to conflict (UNHCR, 2020). Recent clashes between government forces and rebels in Syria provide an excellent example of just how devastating modern-day skirmishes can be – hundreds of thousands dead and millions rendered homeless, creating one of the most significant refugee crises in recorded history (OCHA, 2021) while the Yemeni civil war alongside blocking off critical supplies has resulted into severe famine outbreaks coupled with diseases thereby underscoring disastrous outcomes prolonged hostilities (UN, 2019)

The legacy of violence does not end with the immediate aftermath of a war or conflict. Combatants and civilians suffer psychological trauma, which can have long-term effects, thus perpetuating violent and unstable environments (Shay, 1994). Often, veterans are diagnosed with Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), which makes it difficult for them to reintegrate back into society as citizens again; sometimes, this leads to more aggressive

behaviour or even acts of violence themselves (Hoge et al., 2004).

International relations and geopolitics are also affected by this legacy. Historical conflicts leave deep wounds that foster hatred among nations, which then become distrustful towards each other. The Middle East is one place where such an atmosphere prevails due to ongoing Israeli-Arab wars (Said, 1978). Another example can be seen in Fanon's analysis of how post-colonialism has continuously sparked various African, Asian, and American conflicts.

Dealing with these issues requires all-inclusive measures to reduce immediate causes and foster healing processes among affected communities. This necessitates a clear understanding of why wars happen from historical perspectives and their human tolls if a peaceful world ever has to be achieved. Healing mental health wounds brought about by warfare should go hand in hand with promoting global cooperation while advancing technology geared towards minimizing destructive clashes between people based on tribal lines, instead focusing more efforts on enhancing unity among individuals across borders without necessarily causing any form of hostility amongst them.

Racial Discrimination: The Persistent Stain on Society

Racial discrimination is a primitive act of aggression and psychotic tendency that continues to be prevalent in advanced technological societies. Even today, when globalization and technology have made us more connected than ever before, racial discrimination remains deeply rooted around the world. Even though civil rights have been won through social justice movements and there is greater awareness about these issues, they still manifest themselves in different ways, such as systemic racism or unequal treatment and violent hate crimes being committed daily against people just because they are different from ourselves. Racial prejudice has not been wholly eradicated despite anti-discrimination legislation enacted during civil rights movements over decades gone by.

The Black Lives Matter movement, which gained momentum after the killings of George Floyd and Breonna Taylor, highlighted systemic racism and police brutality in the United States (Harris, 2020). Racial discrimination is not limited to the United States; it is a global phenomenon. In Europe, the rise of far-right political groups has fueled xenophobia and anti-immigrant sentiments. In Myanmar, the persecution of

the Rohingya Muslim minority is a stark example of racial and religious discrimination leading to violence and mass displacement (Human et al., 2019). All these instances serve as positive evidence that racially prejudiced behavior persists within societies that should strive toward equality and inclusivity. Racism has deep roots; it affects all areas, and there are still efforts being made against this stubborn and psychopathological stain.

The modern mind needs to be reminded that the roots of racial discrimination can be found in colonialism and the transatlantic slave trade, which established systems of oppression throughout Western nations. European powers justified their conquests during colonial times by promoting ideas of racial superiority, thereby leading to subjugation as well as exploitation among indigenous populations worldwide alongside forced transportation and enslavement involving millions of Africans (Hochschild, 1998). All these injustices created social structures that continue till today. The American slavery era is the most outstanding example where racism still thrives even after many years. The end of slavery did not mean the end of white supremacy towards black people; there were still laws like Jim Crow in place that enforced racial segregation while also

suppressing African American votes, thereby creating inequalities that are deeply rooted within society (Alexander, 2012). It is against such a backdrop that systemic racism has taken root, affecting various aspects, including education, employment opportunities, and criminal justice systems, among others.

Individual acts of racism may seem harmless, but actually, it goes beyond this. Systemic racism refers to any form of discrimination entrenched within organizations or institutions resulting in unequal treatment on grounds of race—ethnic minorities bear the brunt most times (Bonilla-Silva, 2006). Usually, this kind of discrimination works so subtly: policies and practices are put in place favouring one group over another, leading to cultural norms being maintained and perpetuating racial disparities.

The US criminal justice system clearly shows systemic racism, mainly through mass incarceration rates between blacks/Latinos vis-a-vis whites. For instance, the "war on drugs" approach coupled together with mandatory minimum sentences has affected these communities primarily, causing huge numbers to get locked up behind bars without necessarily having committed serious offences, thus reinforcing negative stereotypes about them

(Lopez, 2016). Similarly, schools have become another site where racial discrimination continues unabated – evident from disparities in school funding, disciplinary actions meted out against students of colour, access to advanced-level courses, etcetera (Kozol, 2005)

The workplace is also a place where racial discrimination happens. Studies have shown that racism is prevalent in hiring, promotions and salaries towards ethnic minorities. Owing to unconscious prejudices and systemic obstacles, people of colour may not be afforded equal opportunities with their white counterparts, notwithstanding there being anti-discrimination laws (Pager and Shepherd, 2008). Racial discrimination affects the economy significantly. Black and Latino families have much less household wealth than whites do; this has been the situation for a long time now. Lack of economic opportunity can keep people poor generation after generation while denying them education and health care, thereby perpetuating systemic bias (Shapiro et al., 2013).

Hate crimes are one way through which racism manifests itself violently or aggressively. Police brutality against blacks in particular, but also other minorities too frequently results in deaths or serious

injuries, such as what happened to George Floyd or Breonna Taylor, respectively, both cases which sparked widespread protests across America demanding justice for victims like them who were killed unfairly just because they happened not to be white-skinned persons (Harris, 2020). These events remind us always about how far we have gone fighting against racialism as well as calling upon every partaker within our justice system, especially those responsible at different levels, starting from the top down right up through the bottom all along until we see complete eradication thereof.

Crimes motivated by hatred towards different races continue happening at an alarming rate globally every day without exception; this has been worsened by increased numbers joining white supremacist groups plus growing popularity among far-right extremists who often become perpetrators themselves involved in various forms, targeting individuals belonging to different religious communities or cultural backgrounds so much so that attacks against such institutions occur more frequently, even than before ever since recorded history began recording incidents related to it, thus proving beyond doubt, continued existence still around us today of which none should feign ignorance anymore lest they arise

anew tomorrow when least expected (Berger, 2018). Sometimes, racial discrimination may not be so blatant but rather take other forms referred to as microaggressions, which are small slights or insults directed against people because of their colour, seeing them as less worthy than others who happen to look-alike themselves. These acts can have severe psychological effects on victims, leading them to low self-esteem and making them feel unwanted or alienated from society, thereby further marginalizing already excluded individuals even more, thus perpetuating long-standing problems associated with race relations (Nadal et al., 2014). For instance, someone might make derogatory comments based on race or use stereotypes when talking about one's intelligence level, competence and character. This has even happened on the football field, where black players are abused and insulted despite their brilliance in football.

For us to effectively deal with racist behaviours, there should always exist a multi-pronged strategy that recognizes its historical antecedents, confronts current realities where it is still deeply entrenched, and commits itself fully towards dismantling anything resembling structures promoting inequality through the

oppression of any kind whatsoever. One way of doing this is by ensuring all schools teach students anti-racist subjects such as history so that they grow up appreciating diversity more instead of fearing what differentiates them from each other (Ladson-Billings, 1995). To be specific, what we need here is an education system that not only looks at past mistakes made but also teaches how best to learn to live together in peace and harmony while celebrating our unique identities without putting down anybody just because he/she does not meet specific cultural criteria deemed acceptable by the majority; this can only happen if teachers themselves become culturally responsive educators equipped with necessary skills and knowledge required to transform lives within classrooms across the world over again. Another thing would involve media houses running public awareness campaigns aimed at changing hearts and minds regarding racism and promoting inclusivity and equality among all races (Bonilla-Silva, 2010).

Structural racism necessitates structural remedies. Governments and institutions must enforce policies that tackle systemic imbalances and foster racial justice. Among other things, this can involve changes in the criminal justice system to fight against

racial profiling and police brutality (Alexander, 2010). For instance, accountability and oversight within police departments could be increased through restructuring, while disparities in incarceration rates can be reduced by revising sentencing guidelines (Gottschalk, 2014). Regarding employment, anti-discrimination policies can help reduce racial discrimination in workplaces. Corporations may introduce anti-bias training programs, put in place recruitment practices that enhance diversity among staff members, or create safe spaces for employees of colour to report cases without fear of victimization (Bell, 1992). As pertains to education, equality should be ensured through the provision of quality education for all students irrespective of their race or ethnicity (Ladson-Billings, 2006).

Community involvement and grassroots activism have played a significant role in challenging racial discrimination and fostering change. The example of the US civil rights movement is illustrative here; it shows how collective action can dismantle racist laws and practices (Branch, 1988). Recently, movements such as Black Lives Matter have been seeking to address broader social justice issues with particular emphasis on systemic racism within

societies globally (Cobb, 2015). Often, these bodies act locally, providing much-needed support services for marginalized communities while engaging in advocacy work to bring about systemic changes necessary for more significant equity. Creating alliances with other groups allows them to increase their influence over policy formulation processes, thereby ensuring that positive gains are made across different fronts (García & Oseguera, 2011).

Individuals need to take responsibility for addressing racism, both within themselves individually and collectively, through acting as allies alongside affected communities against discriminatory systems around us, all too often ignored or perpetuated by people like ourselves. Edwards (2006) defines allyship as "the active, consistent, and arduous practice of unlearning and re-evaluating, in which a person of privilege seeks to work in solidarity with a marginalized group". Allies can support anti-racist efforts by challenging racism wherever it is encountered, educating others about how racism affects everyone adversely, and taking part in demonstrations against racially biased practices, among many other things. However, our personal biases must be acknowledged so that changes may occur towards eliminating those barriers,

preventing fair treatment for everyone regardless of their racial background. Individuals could undergo training on implicit bias, enabling them to become more conscious about their hidden attitudes towards different races, thus enabling them to minimize discriminatory conduct (Greenwald & Banaji, 1995). It starts with us; each individual has the power within themselves to make a difference; therefore, we should strive to promote diversity within our circles, whether in their personal or professional lives, as this will eventually lead to wider acceptance across society.

Societies can advance towards eradicating systemic disparities while at the same time fostering inclusiveness by addressing root causes of prejudice and discrimination based on race or any other social construct. This cannot happen overnight but instead requires sustained commitment from all stakeholders involved, including governments themselves, who need to put in place appropriate mechanisms through which citizens can actively participate in decision-making processes concerning issues related to equal rights, irrespective of one's background. The task may seem daunting; however, if we work together tirelessly enough, these walls will eventually crumble down, paving the way

for new beginnings where every human being is treated reasonably regardless.”

Aggression and Violence: Technology's Double-Edged Sword

Although it has opened up new ways for people to communicate and socialize, technology has also created fresh channels for aggression and violence. Even as it allows individuals to connect globally, the internet has turned into a breeding ground for hate speech, cyberbullying and online harassment. Social media sites were developed to promote communal living but have become battlefields of aggression and hostility (Katz & Rice, 2002). This part examines different contexts in which technology has contributed to an increase in aggressiveness and violence; it looks at how technology can empower and hurt and gives insights into the complex relationship between human behaviour and technology.

Aggression and violence have taken on different forms with the coming of the internet and digital devices. Cyber aggression refers to offensive or harmful acts done through digital means, such as cyberbullying, online harassment, or cyberstalking (Hinduja & Patchin, 2015). The internet provides anonymity that often emboldens persons who would otherwise not engage in aggressive behaviour because

they fear immediate consequences due to the distance between them and their victims and other factors such as lack of physical contact (Kowalski et al., 2014).

Cyberbullying presents a particular challenge, especially among teenagers worldwide. Unlike traditional bullying, cyberbullying can happen any time of the day or night across many time zones; it can also be seen by anyone who has access to a computer, thus amplifying its impact (Tokunaga, 2010). Victims may suffer severe psychological harm, including depression, anxiety, and even suicidal thoughts, where necessary interventions are not made promptly enough to suit any given case of occurrence (Hinduja & Patchin, 2010).

New types of physical violence are now possible through the use of modern technologies, too. The easy Availability of sophisticated weapons like guns and explosives has led to increased levels of violent conflicts and mass shootings (Berkowitz, 2018). In countries where gun control laws are not strict enough, people have easy access to guns, hence making these incidents frequent and more deadly; this shows why there should be stringent measures put in place to prevent such events from happening again (Lankford,

2016). The employment of drones during warfare has enabled attackers to achieve higher precision rates when targeting their enemies, thereby increasing efficiency. However, unfortunately, many times, civilians become victims because they were within striking distance or the wrong persons were targeted at the wrong places, which raises questions over the moral use of technology to facilitate killing from far-off areas (Singer, 2009); Ethics demand that one should not kill innocent souls just because you can do so using a machine. Additionally, cyber war is fought through computers attacking each other's systems with viruses or malware, thus causing damage either directly or indirectly; sometimes, even entire cities may lose electricity supply due to hacking activities directed towards power generation plants, among other critical infrastructures while others are used break into sensitive networks gather proper intel without leaving any traces behind them except those which indicate presence specific state-sponsored agents trying gain illegal access into foreign government agencies' classified databases containing confidential information about national security interests (Clapper, 2018).

The spread of hate speech and extremism has also been driven by technology.

Initially created for social connection, social media platforms have instead become a hotbed for extremist ideologies and hate groups (Berger, 2018). Often, the algorithms these platforms use promote sensational or controversial content, which inadvertently amplifies hate speech while allowing for individual radicalization (Zuckerman, 2020). Extremist groups use platforms to recruit members, spread propaganda and coordinate violent attacks, such as what happened during the Christchurch Mosque shootings in New Zealand (Rieti, 2019). The challenge in dealing with online hate speech and extremism is finding the line between freedom of expression and violence prevention. Content moderation and removal are increasingly expected from social media companies but are seen as censorship by some who oppose them (Flew, 2021). Countries have different laws regarding what can be said online, making it challenging to control harmful material globally.

In addition to enabling aggression or violence, this same technology can also serve as a powerful intervention or prevention. Digital platforms can spread positive messages, raise awareness about societal problems, and connect people with support systems. #MeToo campaign

against sexual harassment reached millions worldwide through its use on different online spaces like Facebook, which showed just how much impact these campaigns can have on achieving social justice through tech innovations alone (Cobb, 2015). Another example would be predictive policing technologies that use data analysis and other resources to identify potential crime hotspots early enough, thus enabling law enforcement agencies to allocate their personnel effectively where needed most (Perry et al., 2013). Nevertheless, there are still fears over civil liberties violations, especially regarding surveillance techniques employed by authorities during investigations into cases involving offline or online violent behaviour via CCTV cameras, etcetera (CCTV Research Group, 2017).

Technology's ability to foster and suppress aggression and violence is both sides of a single coin. Cyberbullying, for example, has only come about because of technological advances; however, these same advances also mean that we can now do more than ever before to prevent such behaviour from occurring in the first place. Therefore, faced with this dual nature of technology, it becomes necessary to adopt an approach that considers not only its potential good but also possible harms and

ethical considerations surrounding their use so that society may benefit most from them.

Killings and Violence: The Brutal Reality of Crime

The advancements in technology have not eliminated the savage character of crime. Sometimes, technology can make violence worse by providing new ways for criminals to commit crimes. The use of firearms during mass shootings demonstrates that progress in technology does not necessarily mean less violence. We have had many mass murders at schools and other places where people gather publicly, like work or parks all across the United States, which has high rates of gun-related homicides each year (Lankford, 2016). No matter how much technological or human rights advances there are, killings and violence continue to be real issues in societies worldwide. The dark side of criminal behaviour reflects deep-seated problems within communities that often stem from social inequities, systemic failures and cultural factors. This part examines various types of homicides and violent acts, their causes as well as consequences at community levels with broader implications on society.

Violent crime is an umbrella term encompassing different types, such as

murder, assault, and domestic violence, among others, like sexual assault. Murder is the most extreme form, where one person deliberately kills another individual (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime [UNODC, 2019]). According to the UNODC report released in 2017, it is estimated that about four hundred sixty-four thousand people were murdered worldwide, but this figure varies significantly from region to region.

Assault and battery are also common forms of violent crime, which usually involve physical attacks causing harm or injury to others. These offences may occur anywhere, including private homes and public places, when conflicts escalate into fights (Kleck, 2005). Domestic Violence Act defines domestic relationship as any intimate relationship between adults who live together or have lived together at some time; related by blood ties; married couples; separated spouses where either party is seeking custody over children jointly conceived, even if they never got married legally; parties dating each other currently or was formerly dating before but no longer do so now while still harbouring feelings towards each other. Hence posing a risk for continued abuse. Sexual violence like rape and sexual assault targets women more than any other group. Offenders are usually

males who take advantage of power differences between genders to enforce their will on victims through acts that violate physical integrity as well as dignity (Koss et al., 1987). In most cases, it has long-term psychological effects because survivors' mental health is damaged permanently, thereby affecting them socially too due to fear of stigmatization, should they disclose what happened, hence remaining silent even if this means enabling the perpetrator to continue his criminal behaviour elsewhere.

The causes behind committing violent crimes are many; they could be individualistic, societal or environmental, among others, therefore making prevention a difficult task sometimes. Lack of education, coupled with poverty, creates fertile grounds for crime since people living under such conditions find themselves in environments conducive to offending each other (Pratt & Cullen, 2005). Communities deprived of resources, including jobs, are prone to high levels of lawlessness where there is nothing else left but survival at all costs, which breeds violence. Racist policies within justice systems fuel disparities, leading blacks to be mistreated by being arrested more frequently and ending up behind bars, thus perpetuating cycles containing both brutality and

incarceration (Alexander, 2010). The Availability of guns in certain nations like America has been associated with increased rates of firearm-related killings and mass shootings as well (Hemenway, 2006). Cultural elements may also contribute to the perpetuation of violent crimes, especially when masculinity becomes toxic alongside the glorification of aggression within societies. When media entertainment or general attitude portrays violence continuously, then its root causes become difficult to address while pushing forward alternative forms of conflict resolution that do not involve the use of force against another person (Katz, 2013).

Violent crime has a significant effect on communities, impacting not just those directly involved but also their families, friends and broader society. Communities with high levels of violence often experience more fear and insecurity among their members, which leads to less social bonding and trust between residents (Sampson et al., 1997). This alienation may fuel further acts of violence as individuals might see this as the only way to protect themselves or retaliate against others. The economic implications are also significant; areas suffering from persistently high crime rates witness declining property values, low business investments, and extra expenditure

on law enforcement and public services (Levitt, 1999). These financial setbacks further entrench inequalities, making it harder for them to escape such violent episodes.

Dealing with killings and aggression calls for a holistic approach that tackles root causes while promoting community-based solutions. Some strategies include:

- Community Policing: Getting police involved in community-oriented policing can help foster relationships between them and the citizens they serve (Gill et al., 2014). By concentrating on joint problem-solving efforts, this strategy seeks to prevent violent incidents before they happen by identifying potential offenders or victims.
- Violence Prevention Programs: Schools should introduce programs to stop violence by addressing its underlying causes (Farrington & Ttofi, 2009). These initiatives usually cover conflict resolution skills training, anger management techniques, and promoting positive behaviours within peer groups.
- Gun Control and Regulation: Areas experiencing frequent gun-related fatalities need to review their

firearm laws to restrict access while reducing risks associated with shootings (Hemenway, 2006). Such measures may involve background checks during purchase or licensing processes, time delays before acquiring guns, and limiting magazine sizes.

- Supporting Victims of Violence: Giving help alongside resources towards recovery after victimization from violent acts plays a significant role in preventing reoccurrence (Logan & Walker, 2004). Among these could be counselling sessions and legal aid services, including safe houses for domestic abuse survivors.

Killings and violence remain harsh realities within the modern world, illustrating deeper problems related to social inequality, institutional racism, and cultural acceptance of aggressive behaviour. Different approaches must be taken when dealing with such issues, which should involve communities on a large scale but also require strong law enforcement measures. Society can work towards a future where much aggression is avoided by addressing the root causes behind conflicts, thus promoting non-violent ways of resolving them.

Hatred and Bitterness: The Roots of Conflict

Hatred and bitterness underlie many of these acts of violence. Hatred and resentment are the most powerful and destructive emotions fueling human conflict. Often arising from deep-seated grievances, historical enmities, and perceived injustices, they can facilitate violence, entrench discrimination, and erect obstacles to reconciliation. In order to comprehend their role in contemporary conflicts, we must look into what perpetuates them so stubbornly and consider how widely they reverberate across both global and local systems.

Much hatred and bitterness are born from events that have left behind scars that continue to hurt long after they are over. Such grudges may last for generations, creating a collective memory bank and influencing attitudes toward others who were not even alive when those things happened. For example, few Israelis or Palestinians alive today still feel bitter about each other only because their parents taught them. Hence, it is all too easy for children brought up by parents with an axe grind against somebody else's culture not to grow up like anything about such cultures either (Said, 1978). Similarly, throughout history, wherever people suffered at one

another's hands during periods marked by significant inequality, some mutual hostility cannot endure indefinitely afterwards unless something drastic changes things permanently.

Hatred can also be caused by perceived injustice, even if no wrong has been done. When individuals or communities think that they have been mistreated or discriminated against, they might develop resentment, leading to aggression or violence, sometimes called "reactive aggression." This frequently happens with racial issues where blacks feel like whites always receive better treatment than themselves due solely to skin colour alone, thus causing deep-seated anger within this community until equal rights are given plus more reparations paid for past mistreatment (Harris, 2020); likewise native Americans will never [stop] fighting back until every treaty signed between US gov't & tribes upheld in full without exception (Smith, 1999).

Another source of bitterness comes from strong identities and loyalties. People tend to form alliances based on shared beliefs, values or backgrounds, which can foster an "us vs them" mindset, mainly when threats against any member's group status exist. This is commonly seen in religion, where different faiths clash over what they believe

their god wants to be done, but it also extends beyond this realm into politics as well; for instance, ethnic cleansing campaigns have been justified by leaders claiming that if everyone speaks the same language, practices the same customs then peace will reign forever more -- such statements only serve further divisions among peoples thereby fueling hatreds (Tajfel & Turner, 1986).

Political leaders or groups can also manipulate hatred and bitterness for personal gain. Such individuals may use rhetoric designed not only to win elections but also to incite violence against perceived enemies while still keeping within limits set by law, thus allowing themselves plausible deniability, later on, should things turn sour, quickly due partly primarily because many nationalist movements rely heavily upon memories of past wrongs committed against particular nations during previous eras combined with fear-mongering about what could happen again unless specific policies adopted immediately. This type of manipulation has been common practice throughout history, including most recently, the Balkan wars, where politicians whipped up support behind them using mainly ethnic nationalism as the basis for their campaigns (Ignatieff, 1993). Society pays a heavy price when hatreds run deep

since they destroy everything around them, like cancer cells, eating away at healthy tissue until nothing remains but dust particles floating aimlessly through space devoid even of hope itself. These emotions tear societies apart, making them susceptible to conflict and preventing society from cohesion, thereby inhibiting peace-building efforts. Besides causing physical harm, these negative emotions leave lasting psychological scars on both individual and community levels. Studies have shown that children who grow up in environments where there is much hatred and violence are more likely to become aggressive themselves and struggle with forming healthy relationships later in life (Cummings et al., 2010).

Thus, hate breeds further hate like nothing else can. Whenever one group attacks another, it invariably leads to retaliatory attacks, perpetuating cycle after cycle of aggression ad infinitum. Until such time when people stop teaching their kids, grudges fought between forefathers or ancestors against other tribes during wars years gone by, or even millenniums ago, these emotions will linger on and on and cause much more violence and destruction. Parents must start imparting virtues, love, kindness, understanding, empathy, reconciliation, forgiveness, patience,

honesty and integrity towards all human beings, regardless of colour, race, religion, gender, sexual orientation, nationality, political affiliation, socio-economic class, educational background, mental and physical health status, age et; only then shall we truly achieve global peace among nations.

The persistence of hatred and bitterness in societies today shows us that technology cannot solve the problems it creates. These two negative emotions may be handed down from one generation to another, generating a never-ending cycle of violence. In some parts, such as the Middle East, age-old disputes are driven by historical injustices combined with religious schisms, thus resulting in continuous acts of hostility (Said 1978). Such deep-rooted feelings can be used by individuals who want people to fight each other, making it hard for peace to prevail permanently.

Conclusion

The fact that we still have savage tendencies even though we live in an era full of technological advancements raises questions on whether or not humanity can progress further or evolve. Wars, racism, aggression, killings, hatred, and resentments continue being witnessed by communities, notwithstanding their achieved scientific milestones, which were supposed to foster knowledge sharing between different cultures, leading towards global harmony. Dealing with these challenges calls for more than just gadgets; there must also be a change in attitude towards others and ourselves. While technology has been blamed for dividing people apart from uniting them, the truth is that it could either bring out the best or the worst in us depending on how responsibly we use it. This thus presents difficulty because fostering empathy worldwide while recognizing and confronting our innermost primitive instincts simultaneously requires embracing universal values based on love for one another expressed through tolerance coupled with non-violence.

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